

User Behavior Based Enhanced Protocol (UBEP) for Secure near Field Communication

Authors : Vinay Gautam, Vivek Gautam

Abstract : With increase in the unauthorized user's access, it is required to increase the security in the Near Field Communication (NFC). In the paper we propose a user behavior based enhanced protocol entitled 'User Behavior based Enhanced Protocol (UBEP)' to increase the security in NFC enabled devices. The UBEP works on the history of interaction of a user with system. The propose protocol considers four different factors (touch, time and distance & angle) of user behavior to know the authenticity or authorization of the users. These factors can be same for a user during interaction with the system. The UBEP uses two phase user verification system to authenticate a user. Firstly the acquisition phase is used to acquire and store the user interaction with NFC device and the same information is used in future to detect the authenticity of the user. The second phase (recognition) uses analysis of current and previous scenario of user interaction and digital signature verification system to finally authenticate user. The analysis of user based input makes a NFC transaction more advance and secure. This security is very tactical because it is completely depends on usage of the device.

Keywords : security, network field communication, NFC protocol

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014